

Preparation of Salicylato and Nitrosalicylato Derivatives of Bis- π -Cyclopentadienyl Molybdenum(VI)-Oxo Dichloride and Bis- π -Indenyl Molybdenum(VI)-Oxo Dichloride

K. C. GOYAL and B. D. KHOSLA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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The salicylato and nitrosalicylato derivatives of (i) bis- π -cyclopentadienyl molybdenum (VI)-oxo dichloride and (ii) bis- π -indenyl molybdenum (VI)-oxo dichloride were obtained by heating salicylic or nitrosalicylic acid with (i) or (ii) in benzene solution. They were found to react with only one mole of the salicylic or the nitrosalicylic acid. The products have been characterised by i. r. spectra.

A large number of derivatives of salicylic acid with metal halides have been reported which fall into three categories of derivatives : (a) Those in which only phenolic hydrogen is replaced, the carboxylic group remaining intact, for example reactions with Ti(IV)¹, Sn(IV)² and Fe(III)³ halides. (b) Those in which the carboxylic group hydrogen is replaced, the phenolic group remaining intact, for example reactions with Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Th(IV) and Si(IV)⁴ halides. (c) Those in which both the phenolic as well as carboxylic group hydrogen atoms have been replaced, for example reactions with W(VI)⁵, WO(IV)⁶ and Ce(III)⁷ halides. These have been termed as 'salicylato' derivatives by Barbieri.⁸ However there is no mention in literature of any reaction between salicylic acid and π -metallocene dihalides. The present communication describes the preparation of 'salicylato' and 'nitrosalicylato' derivatives of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl molybdenum-oxo dichloride and bis- π -indenyl molybdenum-oxo dichloride.

These derivatives have been prepared by refluxing the above named compounds with salicylic acid (or nitrosalicylic acids) in benzene until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. Two mole ratios (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) were tried but it was found that one molecule of the molybdenum-oxo dichloride reacted with only one molecule of salicylic acid (or a nitrosalicylic acid). Analytical data and physical characteristics of the above derivatives are given in Table 1. These compounds are either dark violet or almost black in colour and are stable under dry conditions. The derivatives are non-volatile ; they do not sublime even in vacuum. They are sparingly soluble in benzene, dioxane, THF and are almost insoluble in petroleum ether and diethyl ether.

Experimental

Special precautions were taken to exclude moisture and all operations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Benzene was dried over sodium metal. Bis- π -cyclopentadienyl molybdenum(VI)-oxo dichloride and bis- π -indenyl molybdenum(VI)-oxo dichloride were prepared by the method reported earlier.^{9,10} 3-nitro, 5-nitro and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acids¹¹⁻¹³ were prepared from salicylic acid by standard methods. Infrared spectra (in KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord Model-137, spectrophotometer. Molybdenum was estimated as 8-hydroxyquinolate. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined by the combustion method.

Preparation of salicylato derivatives of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl molybdenum(VI)-oxo dichloride

To 1.047 g (0.0033 mole) of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl molybdenum-oxo dichloride in 125 ml dry benzene was added 0.461 g (0.0033 mole) salicylic acid and the reaction mixture was refluxed. Evolution of hydrogen chloride began after half an hour and the contents gradually turned dark violet. The refluxing was continued until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The resulting mixture was then evaporated to dryness. On washing the residue with petroleum ether a dark violet coloured crystalline compound was obtained.

A similar procedure was adopted for the preparation of 3-nitro, 5-nitro and 3,5-dinitrosalicylato derivatives of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl molybdenum-oxo dichloride and salicylato, 3-nitro, 5-nitro and 3,5-dinitrosalicylato derivatives of bis- π -indenyl molybdenum-oxo dichloride.

TABLE 1—DETAILS OF PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF SALICYLATO AND NITROSALICYLATO DERIVATIVES OF $(C_5H_5)_2MoOCl_2$ AND $(C_9H_7)_2MoOCl_2$

Compound	$(C_5H_5)_2MoOCl_2$ taken (g)	Amount of corresponding salicylic acid taken (g)	Colour of the compound	Analytical data							
				Metal		Carbon		Hydrogen		Nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
$(\pi-C_5H_5)_2MoO(C_7H_4O_8)$	1.047	0.461	dark violet	25.3	25.39	53.6	53.9	3.4	3.7		
$(\pi-C_5H_5)_2MoO(C_7H_8O_5N)$ 3-	0.877	0.512	-do-	22.4	22.69	47.8	48.2	3.1	3.07	3.1	3.3
$(\pi-C_5H_5)_2MoO(C_7H_8O_5N)$ 5-	0.908	0.531	blackish violet	22.3	22.69	48.0	48.2	3.0	3.07	3.12	3.3
$(\pi-C_5H_5)_2MoO(C_7H_8O_7N_2)$ 3,5-	0.626	0.456	blackish violet	20.4	20.5	43.2	43.5	2.4	2.56	5.78	5.98
$(\pi-C_9H_7)_2MoO(C_7H_4O_8)$	$(C_9H_7)_2MoOCl_2$ taken (g) 1.0325	0.345	blackish violet	20.1	20.08	62.4	62.8	3.5	3.76	—	
$(\pi-C_9H_7)_2MoO(C_7H_8O_5N)$ 3-	1.181	0.5233	-do-	18.13	18.3	56.98	57.3	3.0	3.2	2.5	2.67
$(\pi-C_9H_7)_2MoO(C_7H_8O_5N)$ 5-	0.9581	0.4245	Black	18.06	18.3	57.1	57.3	3.1	3.2	2.49	2.67
$(\pi-C_9H_7)_2MoO(C_7H_8O_7N_2)$ 3,5	0.6195	0.342	Black	16.68	16.9	52.67	52.8	2.63	2.8	4.73	4.9
$MoOCl_2(C_7H_4O_8)$	$MoOCl_4$ taken (g) 0.7569	0.412	Black	29.8	30.0	26.1	26.3	1.0	1.2	22.0	22.2
$MoO(C_7H_4O_8)_2$	0.6807	0.7397	Violet black	24.8	25.00	43.55	43.7	2.0	2.08	—	

Results and Discussion

The compositions, as derived from elemental analysis of the various salicylato derivatives, suggest that one molecule each of $(C_5H_5)_2MoOCl_2$ or $(C_9H_7)_2MoOCl_2$ reacts with one molecule of salicylic acid (or nitrosalicylic acid), and both the chlorine atoms of molybdenum-oxo dichlorides are replaced by a salicylato group or a nitrosalicylato group. The chlorine atoms are eliminated as hydrogen chloride. The formation of the derivatives may be represented by the following general equation :

where H_2A = salicylic or nitrosalicylic acid, one hydrogen being from the -COOH group and the other from the -OH group. R = cyclopentadienyl or indenyl group.

I.R. spectra of the salicylato derivatives

The infrared spectra of the various salicylato derivatives were recorded in the region $4000-670\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The presence of $C_5H_5^-$ ring in these compounds is inferred

by the i.r. absorption bands at $\sim 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H stretching), at 1150 cm^{-1} and 1030 cm^{-1} (C-H in-plane deformation) and at $860-840\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H out-of-plane deformation). Sharp and strong absorption bands in the range $1460-1440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the C-C stretching (asymmetric ring breathing), and also the π -bonding of the ring with the molybdenum-oxo group.

The presence of indenyl group is indicated by the usual peaks due to $C_9H_7^-$ ring. The absorption bands due to phenyl part of the indenyl group appeared at 1610 cm^{-1} and 1450 cm^{-1} (C-C stretching), at $\sim 1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H in-plane and out-of-plane deformations respectively). A band at 710 cm^{-1} may be due to the methylene rocking vibration (since indene itself shows an absorption band at $\sim 700\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Metal carboxylate complexes show characteristic absorption bands in the region $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (asymmetric -O-C-O-stretching) and at $\sim 1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (symmetric stretching of carboxylate group)¹⁴. Another group of strong absorption bands in the region $1040-1010\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $825-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been considered to be due to the metal-carboxylate linkage¹⁵. In cyclopentadienyl

and indenyl metal-phenoxy derivatives, the i.r. bands in the region $\sim 1480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been attributed to the metal-phenoxy linkage.¹⁶

In these salicylato and nitrosalicylato derivatives where the molybdenum-oxo group is bonded to phenoxy as well as carboxylato groups, the i.r. spectra show a variation in the observed frequencies of metal-phenoxy and metal-carboxylato linkages. A. K. Babko et al.,¹⁷ have inferred that metal salicylates containing a free phenolic group (M-O OC-C₆H₄OH) absorb in the region $1357\text{-}1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, while those in which the phenolic as well as carboxylic group hydrogens have been replaced

(M lack this absorption characteristic but

show absorption bands in the region $1580\text{-}1527 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1402\text{-}1366 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are due to the carboxylato group. Additional bands at $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been attributed to the metal-carboxylate linkage (O-C-O-M). These salicylato and nitrosalicylato derivatives do not show any i.r. bands in the region $1357\text{-}1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (showing absence of free phenolic group), but exhibit absorption bands at 1580 cm^{-1} and $\sim 1380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that both phenolic as well as carboxylic group hydrogen atoms have been replaced. Absorption band at $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to metal-carboxylate linkage while another band at $\sim 1480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to the metal-phenoxy linkage. Further support for the structure of the salicylato derivatives can be derived from the comparison between the i.r. spectra of these derivatives and those of (i) monosalicylato molybdenum (VI)-oxo dichloride, (C₇H₄O₈)MoOCl₂ and (ii) disalicylato molybdenum (VI)-oxide (C₇H₄O₈)₂MoO (these have been prepared by refluxing a one mole proportion of MoOCl₄ with one and two mole proportions respectively of salicylic acid in benzene, until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased). The compounds (i) and (ii) thus obtained show bands neither in the region $\sim 3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ nor in the region $1357\text{-}1310$ (indicating absence of the free phenolic group), but show bands at 1565 cm^{-1} ($1586\text{-}27 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region) and at 1380 cm^{-1} ($1402\text{-}1360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region) due to carboxylate group and at $\sim 1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in the region $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) due to a metal carboxylate linkage. Metal-phenoxy linkage band is observed at 1475 cm^{-1} .

A very sharp band at 980 cm^{-1} observed in these compounds is due to Mo=O stretching frequencies. The sharp bands at $1548\text{-}1520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1360\text{-}1337 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to the presence of nitro groups.¹⁸

The following tentative structure may be proposed for the salicylato derivatives.

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